

Gender disparities in reasons for part-time work in Turkey

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Abstract: This paper investigates the reasons for part-time work in Turkey, with a particular focus on gender disparities. Using microdata from the Turkish Household Labour Force Survey conducted by the Turkish Statistical Institute, multinomial regression models are used to examine the demographic and work-related factors influencing reasons for part-time work. Rather than the traditional categorisation of part-time work as voluntary or involuntary, this research explores the reasons separately, providing a more comprehensive view of understanding the reasons driving individuals to choose part-time employment. The findings reveal that gender differences in reasons for part-time work are consistent with societal expectations and gender roles. As expected, individuals working part-time due to care responsibilities are mostly women, while men have a greater share in the reason for could not find a full-time job. However, being married and increasing the number of people in the household boost the probability of solely women's part-time work due to care responsibilities but not men's. Similarly, age, registration, occupation, and sector variables are more determinants for men compared to women in the category of could not find a full-time job. Differences between genders are less common in other reasons for part-time work.

Keywords: Part-time work, reasons, Turkish labour market, gender disparities.

Disparidades de género nas razões para o trabalho a tempo parcial na Turquia

Resumo: Este artigo investiga as razões para o trabalho a tempo parcial na Turquia, com um foco particular nas disparidades de género. Utilizando microdados da Pesquisa de Força de Trabalho Doméstico Turco realizada pelo Instituto Turco de Estatísticas, modelos de regressão multinomial são utilizados para examinar os fatores demográficos e relacionados ao trabalho que influenciam as razões para o trabalho a tempo parcial. Em vez da categorização tradicional do trabalho a tempo parcial como voluntário ou involuntário, esta pesquisa explora as razões separadamente, proporcionando uma visão mais abrangente para compreender as razões que levam os indivíduos a escolherem o emprego a tempo parcial. Os resultados revelam que as diferenças de género nas razões para o trabalho a tempo parcial estão de acordo com as expectativas sociais e os papéis de género. Como esperado, indivíduos que trabalham a tempo parcial devido a responsabilidades de cuidado são principalmente mulheres, enquanto os homens têm uma participação maior na razão de não conseguirem encontrar um emprego em tempo integral. No entanto, ser casado e o número de pessoas no domicílio aumenta a probabilidade do trabalho a tempo parcial das mulheres devido a responsabilidades de cuidado, mas não dos homens. Da mesma forma, idade, registro, ocupação e variáveis do setor são mais determinantes para os homens em comparação com as mulheres na categoria de não conseguir encontrar um emprego em tempo integral. As diferenças entre os géneros são menos comuns em outras razões para o trabalho a tempo parcial.

Palavras-chave: Trabalho a tempo parcial, razões, mercado de trabalho turco, disparidades de género.

1. Introduction

Part-time work has gained increasing importance in most countries over the past decades, and millions of people around the world work part-time for various reasons (ILO, 2016a). Part-time work, considered to be one of flexible (Russell et al., 2009; Wheatley, 2017), atypical (Anxo et al., 2012; Giesecke, 2009), or non-standard working arrangements (Kalleberg, 2000; ILO, 2016a), is defined as shorter working hours than comparable full-time work in the International Labour Organization (ILO) Part-Time Work Convention, 1994 (No. 175) (Fagan et al., 2014). Legal thresholds (generally 30 or 35 hours per week) separating part-time work from full-time work vary among countries (Kalleberg, 2000; Delsen, 1998). In Turkey, this threshold is determined as "two-thirds of the peer work done with a full-time work contract in the workplace" instead of a specific hours cut-off, as specified in Article 6 of the Regulation Related to the Labour Law on Working Hours. However, considering the provision "in general terms, working time is 45 hours maximum per week", as indicated in Article 63 of the Labour Law, the threshold is a maximum of 30 hours.

Could not find a full-time job, education, illness or disability, care and housework responsibilities, and personal or family obligations are the common reasons for working part-time. However, their incidence varies between countries, genders, as well as age groups (see Eurostat (2023) for European countries, Patterson (2018) for Canada, Cassidy and Parsons (2017) for Australia, Dunn (2018) for the US, Blázquez Cuesta and Moral Carcedo (2014) for women in Denmark, the Netherlands, France, Italy, and Spain). Generally, workers between the ages of 15 and 24 mostly work part-time due to education. Furthermore, could not find a full-time job for men and childcare for women are common reasons for part-time work.

The traditional approach to reasons for part-time work is to categorise the reasons as voluntary and involuntary (Tilly, 1991) or economic and non-economic (Canon et al., 2014). Involuntary part-time and part-time for economic reasons often mean the same and describe part-time workers who would prefer full-time work (Nardone, 1995; Dunn, 2018). The related empirical studies in the literature about the reasons for part-time work are those that focus on the determinants of involuntary part-time work (see Cam, 2012; Valletta et al., 2020; Pech et al., 2021; Görmüş & Erdoğan, 2017; Duzgun Oncel & Eris Dereli, 2023; Insarauto, 2021). They have combined part-time work reasons as involuntary (could not find full-time work or slack work) and voluntary (other reasons). There have also been papers using cluster analysis that categorise part-time workers according to part-time work reasons (see Maynard et al., 2006; Björk et al., 2020). Other studies have investigated working part-time versus working full-time or being out of labour force (see Tijdens, 2002; Long & Jones, 1981; Kjeldstad & Nymoen, 2012; Dieckhoff et al., 2016; Palaz et al., 2013; Duzgun Oncel & Eris Dereli, 2015; Güneş & Acun, 2015).

In this study, we have analysed the reasons for part-time work separately, rather than as involuntary or voluntary. We have predicted probabilities for reasons by multinomial regression models using Turkish Household Labour Force Surveys microdata. We have also taken into account gender disparities. Thus, we aim to provide a more detailed research on the reasons for part-time work in the literature.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: The second section discusses part-time employment motivations, and part-time work in Turkey. The third section introduces

methodology. In the fourth section, we present results. The last section discusses the results and concludes the paper.

2. Part-Time Employment Motivations, and Part-Time Work in Turkey

The OECD countries' part-time employment rates are displayed in Figure 1. Eastern European nations have the lowest rates of part-time employment, whereas northern and western Europe have the highest rates. Especially in the Netherlands, the first part-time economy in the world (Visser, 2002), part-time employment is prevalent among both men and women, with nearly three-fifths of women working part-time. Turkey has a slightly lower rate of part-time employment than the OECD average. The variations in the incidence of part-time work can be influenced by institutional determinants such as sectoral composition of the labour market, labour and product market regulations, legal working hour regulations, tax systems, the availability of childcare, and normative contexts, including societal attitudes towards gender-specific working hours (Barbieri et al., 2019). Based on a sample consisting of companies in 21 European countries, Anxo et al. (2012) have indicated that country-specific characteristics have a stronger influence on the variations in the ratio of part-time workers at the establishment level compared to industry-specific factors.

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Figure 1. Part-time employment rates in OECD countries (2020)
(Source: OECD, 2023)

Offering flexibility and reduced working hours, part-time work has been identified as a potential solution to achieve work-life balance and reconcile work commitments with personal and family responsibilities (Lyonette, 2015; Russell et al., 2009). In addition, studies have revealed that part-time work is associated with greater job and life satisfaction among men (Wheatley, 2017) and life satisfaction for women (Higgins et al., 2000). Gash et al. (2012) have found that women who switch from full-time work to part-time work increase their life satisfaction in the UK and Germany. Part-time work has been preferred by more women than men due to various factors, including the unequal distribution of caregiving and housework responsibilities, societal expectations, and gender

roles (Fortier, 2020; Lyonette, 2015). Hakim, who has made great contributions to the literature on women's employment and sex discrimination, discussed more part-time employment of women in her well-known work, preference theory. According to Hakim (2006), women choose between three different lifestyles: home-centred, work-centred, or adaptive. Adaptive includes the majority of women who desire to balance work and family; therefore, part-time work is attractive to this group. Less than 40% of the world's labour force is made up of women, but they account for 57% of part-time workers. The vast majority of part-time employment worldwide is held by women (ILO, 2016b). However, almost the same number of men and women (nearly 1.5 million for each) work part-time in Turkey, although the part-time work ratio of women (19.01%) is much higher than the men's (8.61%) (see Table 1). This is mainly the result of very low female labour force participation¹. Turkey is one of the countries with the highest gender gap in labour force participation rates (Gevrek & Gevrek, 2023; Aldan, 2021).

Table 1. Reasons for part-time work in Turkey (2020)

Age groups	15-64			15-24			25-54			55-64		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
Reasons (%)												
Care responsibilities	6.24	0.35	12.12	2.75	0.1	6.53	8.72	0.51	15.29	1.03	0.18	2.31
Education	8.26	10.22	6.31	41.65	43.76	38.65	0.52	0.76	0.33	0	0	0
Illness or disability	3.48	3.52	3.44	0.71	0.78	0.62	3.36	3.59	3.17	6.96	6.26	8.02
Personal or family obligations	6.08	4.88	7.28	6.03	5.26	7.14	5.69	3.71	7.27	7.58	7.6	7.53
Could not find a full-time job	15.44	23.25	7.64	12.66	16.16	7.7	18.39	30.67	8.55	7.76	10.92	2.94
Nature of the job	60.49	57.77	63.21	36.18	33.94	39.38	63.33	60.76	65.38	76.68	75.04	79.2
Number of observations	26,174	12,827	13,347	4,698	2,795	1,903	16,029	6,822	9,207	5,447	3,210	2,237
Population size (x1000)	3,064	1,531	1,533	584	343	241	1,945	865	1,080	535	323	212
% within total employment	11.85	8.61	19.01	17.12	14.85	21.91	9.76	6.35	17.19	21.47	17.81	31.29

Source: Authors' calculations based on Household Labour Force Survey, with sample weights.

As shown in Table 1, the part-time work rate is higher in the 15-24 (17.12%) and 55-64 (21.47%) age groups than in the 25-54 (9.76%) age group in Turkey. However, the majority of part-time workers are between the ages of 25 and 54 (nearly 2 million). According to the reasons for part-time work, more than half of part-time workers' main reason is nature of the job, for both men (57.77%) and women (63.21%). This reason is widespread, even among youth (36.18%). It is followed by care responsibilities for women (12.12%) and could not find a full-time job for men (23.25%). These reasons reach their highest incidence for those between the ages of 25 and 54 (15.29% and 30.67%, respectively). Similar to other countries, it is common for workers between the ages of 15 and 24 (41.65%) to work part-time for educational reasons. In addition, the least frequent reasons for part-time employment are illness or disability (3.48%) and personal or family obligations (6.08%).

Part-time work has a decisive role in women's participation in employment. Because if part-time employment didn't exist, given the choice between a full-time job and no work hours, women would choose the latter (Booth and Van Ours, 2013). Studies have documented that part-time work can be seen as a way to increase female employment (Barbieri et al., 2019; Stavrou et al., 2015; Euwals & Hogerbrugge, 2006).

¹ Interested readers can refer to İlkaraçan (2012) for reasons of low female labour force participation and Çakır (2008) for women's exclusion from working life in Turkey.

Some researchers have paid attention to men working part-time despite their minority in labour market. Larsson and Björk (2017) have stated that the desire to be an included father is an important reason for part-time work in interviews with Swedish fathers who choose parental part-time work. Bünning (2020) has shown that fathers are more involved in child care and housework when they work part-time in Germany. According to Delsen (1995), the unequal treatment of part-time work is the main reason for men's reluctance to work part-time and remain in full-time employment. Additionally, cultural differences also contribute to understanding the limited number of men opting for part-time work.

Students and young adults have also become increasingly interested in part-time work. In addition to financial support, many university students work part-time for various reasons, such as gaining work experience and enhancing their social lives (Hall, 2010; Ford et al., 1995; Richardson et al., 2009). Robotham (2012) has emphasised that the positive outcomes of part-time work (organising time, improving communication skills, increasing self-confidence and motivation, etc.) are more reported than the negative outcomes (reduction in leisure time, feeling tired, less reading, etc.) in a survey of full-time undergraduates.

On the other hand, part-time work can be a viable option to smooth the transition to retirement for older individuals (Fagan et al., 2014; Gannon and Roberts, 2011). Working part-time, they may gradually reduce their working hours and responsibilities and avoid sudden and complete withdrawal from the labour force (Kantarci & Van Soest, 2008). They may also prefer part-time work due to health problems (Allaart & Bellmann, 2007).

Part-time employment has become a useful tool to improve the social inclusion, income, and working conditions of persons with disabilities and health problems because it enables these individuals to strike a far better balance between their personal and health requirements and their working lives (Pagan, 2007). Schur (2003) has found that workers with disabilities are more likely to be part-time work due to health problems, rather than factors like income limits or discrimination. She has suggested that despite the drawbacks, such as lower pay, part-time work offers employment opportunities that would otherwise be inaccessible.

From the labour demand side, part-time work can allow employers to adjust working hours to cyclical or changing economic conditions more easily, facilitating the arrangement of production and labour costs (Buddelmeyer et al., 2008). Zeytinoglu (1992) has listed the reasons for hiring part-time workers as flexibility in scheduling work and in employment decisions, lower wages and benefits, changes in macroeconomic environment, employee preferences, employee suitability, and unavailability of full-time workers. However, she has suggested that flexibility in scheduling work and employees' preferences have major significance, while savings in wages and benefits have minor significance. In addition, Sandor (2011) has stated that part-time work may even increase total labour costs due to fixed costs such as recruitment, training, and social security.

Macroeconomic conditions can affect part-time employment. For example, it is observed that part-time employment rates increase during recessions (Kang et al., 2020). In particular, involuntary part-time employment rates rise along with unemployment rates (Fagan et al., 2014; Duzgun Oncel & Eris Dereli, 2023). Although involuntary part-time employment may be thought to be a strategy to avoid layoffs, Reynolds and Wenger (2010) have found that using part-time work as a means to reduce working hours does not

alleviate the effects of recessions on workers but instead leads to higher unemployment, and the relationship between involuntary part-time work and unemployment is stronger among older workers.

3. Methodology

3.1. Method

Multinomial models are employed in the analysis of unordered categorical outcome variables with more than two categories, such as choice among political candidates, how to commute to work, or occupation. Usually, multinomial logit or multinomial probit models are used to estimate these kinds of models. However, unlike the multinomial logit model, the multinomial probit model is not based on the independence from irrelevant alternatives (IIA) assumption (Greene, 2018; Gujarati, 2014).

The reasons for part-time work are the focus of this study. Considering the potential relationship among the alternatives in the outcome variable, which has multiple choices, we prefer using multinomial probit regression models. Joint and separate probit regression models are estimated for male and female part-time workers in order to investigate the differential effects of demographics and work-related variables on part-time work reasons.

The multinomial probit model with the utility of the j th choice can be expressed as follows:

$$U_{ij} = x'_{ij}\beta + \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, J.$$

The errors are joint normally distributed,

$$[\varepsilon_{i1}, \varepsilon_{i2}, \dots, \varepsilon_{ij}] \sim N[0, \Sigma]$$

It is assumed that U_{ij} is the maximum utility among the J utilities when the i th observation determines choice j . The log likelihood term associated with the alternative q choice is:

$$\Pr[\text{choice}_{iq}] = \Pr[U_{iq} > U_{ij}, \text{ all } q \neq j]$$

$$\Pr[\text{choice}_{iq}] = \Pr[\varepsilon_{i1} - \varepsilon_{iq} < (x_{iq} - x_{i1})'\beta, \dots, \varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_{iq} < (x_{iq} - x_{ij})'\beta]$$

It represents the cumulative probability derived from a normal distribution with $(J-1)$ variables. Flexibility in handling correlated choices and capturing complex relationships among the alternatives are the main advantages of the multinomial probit model (Cameron and Trivedi, 2005; Greene, 2018). In papers examining the reasons for part-time work, logistic (see Cam, 2012; Pech et al., 2021; Görmüş & Erdoğan, 2017) and probit (see Duzgun Oncel & Eris Dereli, 2023; Insarauto, 2021) models for binary outcomes are generally used because the reasons are divided into two categories: voluntary and involuntary. Gannon and Roberts (2011) analyse work decisions, which consist of three choices (part-time work, full-time work, and non-working), using the multinomial probit model.

3.2. Data and Variables

The data we use is based on the Household Labour Force Survey (2020), conducted by the Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT). The administrative microdata, covering all settlements in Turkey and all weeks of the year, includes information on the demographic and working status of individuals such as age, education level, economic activity, occupation, employment status, and working hours. We restrict the age of the sample to

those between 15 and 64, and we use sample weights in all calculations. The data set we analysed consists of a total of 26,174 part-time workers, of whom 12,827 are male and 13,347 are female.

In this study, we are interested in why part-time workers opt for part-time work. Therefore, we use the variable in the dataset that responds to the question "Why are you working in a part-time job?". We combine three subcategories of care responsibilities for children, incapacitated adults, and both into one category, and drop the 'other' category, which includes 163 observations, from the data set because it is not suitable for producing reliable estimates. As a result, we arrange the responses of the part-time workers as the dependent variable, which consists of six categories: care responsibilities, education, illness or disability, personal or family obligations, could not find a full-time job, and nature of the job.

Independent variables include various demographics and work-related information about individuals. Demographic variables are gender (male; female), marital status (single; married), age, household size (person), and education² (in years). Work-related variables are registration to social security institutions (registered; unregistered), occupation³ (career; earner), sector (agriculture; industry; service), and employment status (paid, salaried, or casual; employer/self-employed; unpaid family workers). We control regional differences at the NUTS-1 level in all regressions. Although having children, the number of children, and the age of children are important factors in the preference for part-time work, we are not able to utilise them in the analysis because the data set does not provide child-related variables.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents detailed descriptive statistics on reasons for part-time work, providing insights into the demographic and work-related characteristics associated with each category. Table 2 indicates that a significant proportion of overall part-time workers in Turkey are married (69.98%), unregistered (71.47%), and working in earner occupations (87.67%). The mean age is 39.461, the typical household size is 4.226, and the mean education level stands at approximately 8 years.

Gender: The gender distribution within reasons for part-time work categories reveals significant disparities. Notably, an overwhelming 97.20% of individuals with part-time work due to care responsibilities are women, while 75.25% of those citing the could not find a full-time job are men. Additionally, 59.91% of individuals working part-time due to personal or family obligations are women, whereas 61.82% of those involved in part-time work for educational reasons are men.

² This variable is evaluated according to the latest graduated educational institution on a yearly basis: 0 for not having completed any institution, 5 for primary school, 8 for lower secondary school, 12 for upper secondary school, 16 for a university degree, and 20 for a postgraduate degree.

³ Following Higgins et al. (2000), 1-2 of one-digit ISCO-08 codes define as career, and 3-9 of one-digit ISCO-08 codes define as earner.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for variables by part-time work reasons

Reasons	Care responsibilities		Education		Illness or disability		Personal or family obligations		Could not find a full-time job		Nature of the job		Total	
	Number of obs.	% within groups*	Number of obs.	% within groups*	Number of obs.	% within groups*	Number of obs.	% within groups*	Number of obs.	% within groups*	Number of obs.	% within groups*	Number of obs.	% within groups*
Total	1,339	6.24	1,923	8.26	862	3.48	1,184	6.08	3,351	15.44	17,515	60.49	26,174	100
Gender														
Male	33	2.80	1,214	61.82	431	50.56	443	40.09	2,451	75.25	8,255	47.72	12,827	49.97
Female	1,306	97.20	709	38.18	431	49.44	741	59.91	900	24.75	9,260	52.28	13,347	50.03
Marital status														
Single	98	6.67	1,908	98.91	143	18.36	327	30.83	1,064	32.70	3,652	22.92	7,192	30.02
Married	1,241	93.33	15	1.09	719	81.64	857	69.17	2,287	67.30	13,863	77.08	18,982	69.98
Registration to SSI														
Registered	269	23.16	931	54.00	103	12.07	253	23.47	549	17.07	4,842	29.99	6,947	28.53
Unregistered	1,070	76.84	992	46.00	759	87.93	931	76.53	2,802	82.93	12,673	70.01	19,227	71.47
Occupation														
Career	65	4.62	48	3.56	12	1.40	89	9.54	131	3.96	2,689	17.37	3,034	12.33
Earners	1,274	93.58	1,875	96.44	850	98.60	1,095	90.46	3,220	96.04	14,826	82.63	23,140	87.67
Sector														
Agriculture	469	29.52	615	25.09	433	44.62	339	23.54	782	20.61	10,218	51.69	12,856	41.35
Industry	343	27.96	318	19.00	169	21.10	279	23.87	1,062	33.38	1,672	11.10	3,843	17.37
Service	527	42.52	990	55.90	260	34.29	566	52.59	1,507	46.01	5,625	37.22	9,475	41.28
Employment status														
Paid, salaried, or casual	348	32.77	1,095	63.63	215	29.74	362	35.71	2,095	65.73	4,765	31.67	8,880	39.81
Employer/Self-employed	439	31.06	29	1.68	364	41.20	354	30.84	948	25.66	6,638	36.97	8,772	31.71
Unpaid family workers	552	36.18	799	34.69	283	29.06	468	33.45	308	8.61	6,112	31.37	8,522	28.48
	Mean*	Std. Error*	Mean*	Std. Error*	Mean*	Std. Error*	Mean*	Std. Error*	Mean*	Std. Error*	Mean*	Std. Error*	Mean*	Std. Error*
Age	35.566	0.263	18.444	0.083	48.806	0.450	41.546	0.495	37.909	0.233	42.382	0.117	39.461	0.102
Household size	4.933	0.072	4.751	0.053	3.883	0.093	4.107	0.093	4.244	0.047	4.108	0.023	4.226	0.018
Education	7.219	0.163	9.622	0.071	4.987	0.142	8.231	0.171	7.806	0.093	8.159	0.048	8.061	0.037

Note: * calculated with sample weights. Percentages may not sum due to rounding.

Source: Authors' calculations based on Household Labour Force Survey (2020).

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Marital Status: Marital status demonstrates variations across reasons for part-time work. Single individuals dominate the category of education (98.91%), while married individuals constitute the majority in the care responsibilities (93.33%), and illness or disability (81.64%) categories.

Registration to SSI: Unregistered individuals are prevalent in most categories, particularly in the illness or disability (87.93%) and could not find a full-time job (82.93%) reasons. Nevertheless, the rate of registered part-time workers is higher in education (54%) category.

Occupation: Occupational characteristics show almost no difference among the reasons for working part-time. Those working in career occupations make up a small proportion across all categories. The reason with the highest proportion of individuals working in career occupations is the nature of the job, accounting for only 17.37%.

Sector: Substantial differences can also be seen in the sectoral distribution among reasons for part-time work. For instance, agriculture is a prominent sector for those citing the nature of the job as a reason (51.69%), while the service sector dominates personal or family obligations (52.59%) and education (55.90%) reasons. The industry sector, comprising 17.37% of total part-time workers, attains its highest ratio in the category of could not find a full-time job (33.32%).

Employment Status: The employment status of part-time workers varies across categories. Paid, salaried, or casual workers constitute a significant proportion in the could not find a full-time job (65.73%) and education (63.63%) categories, while employer or self-employed individuals are more prevalent in the illness and disability (41.20%) and nature of the job (36.97%) categories.

Age: The mean age of part-time workers differs across reasons for part-time work. Workers citing education as a reason for part-time employment have a relatively low mean age of 18.444, indicating that this category comprises younger individuals, also shown in Table 1. Conversely, those with illness or disability as the reason for part-time work have the highest mean age at 48.806, suggesting that health-related concerns are more prevalent among older individuals opting for part-time work.

Household Size: Individuals working part-time due to care responsibilities have the largest mean household size at 4.933, signifying that care responsibilities often involve larger family units. The reason for illness and disability has a relatively lower mean household size at 3.883.

Education: The mean education levels of part-time workers vary across reasons for part-time work. Those indicating education as the reason for part-time work display a higher mean education level of 9.622, implying that individuals pursuing educational goals generally achieve higher levels of education. Conversely, individuals with illness and disability (4.987) and care responsibilities (7.219) exhibit a lower mean education level.

4.2. Multinomial Probit Models

Table 3 presents multinomial probit regression estimates for total, male, and female. We present average marginal effects instead of coefficients in the estimation results to make the interpretation of the effect of the variables on part-time work reasons easier. The interpretation is provided for each specified category, considering gender disparities. Moreover, predicted probabilities for specific ages are illustrated in Figure 2, as the impact of age on part-time work reasons may differ across ages.

Care Responsibilities: Results for total part-time workers indicate that women are more likely to work part-time due to care responsibilities. The estimated magnitude of the marginal effect of female (0.0999) is relatively high when considering the ratio of care responsibilities (6.24%) among part-time workers, underscoring the gendered nature of caregiving roles. It is obviously seen that the effects of demographic characteristics and work-related factors vary between genders in this category. For women, being married (0.1222), increasing the number of people in the household (0.012), and working in industry (0.133) and service (0.0682) sectors raise the probability of working part-time due to care responsibilities. Conversely, working in career occupations (0.1062), being paid, salaried, or casual worker (0.032), and being an employer or self-employed (0.0406) decrease it. In men, only occupation exhibits a statistically significant effect on this reason; however, its magnitude (0.0039) is notably smaller compared to women's (0.1062). In addition, the increase in age (0.0036) reduces the probability of working part-time due to care responsibilities in women (on average), but Figure 2 reveals that the probability climbs until the age of 25, then gradually declines.

Education: Among overall part-time workers, an increase in age (0.0131) and household size (0.0033), being married (0.0505), being unregistered (0.0552), working in career occupations (0.0348), being paid, salaried, or a casual worker (0.01), and being an employer or self-employed (0.0198) diminishes the likelihood of working part-time due to education. Notably, Figure 2 shows that the probability has a sharp decline until the age of 30. Conversely, education in years (0.0021) and working in the industry (0.026) and service (0.0273) sectors elevates this probability. The factors influencing part-time work due to education exhibit similarity across genders, with identical signs of marginal effects. However, education in years and employment status variables are not statistically significant for women.

Illness or Disability: The findings from the multinomial probit model reveal that men (0.0082) are more inclined to engage in part-time work due to illness or disability. Similar to the education reason, the effects of variables show no discernible gender differences. Age, being unregistered, and working in the industry and service sectors positively affect the probability of working part-time due to illness or disability. On the other hand, education, being married, and working in career occupations have a negative impact. It is important to note that marital status for men and registration to SSI for women do not reach statistical significance.

Personal or Family Obligations: Another category of part-time work reason where women (0.023) exhibit a higher inclination than men are personal or family obligations. Among all part-time workers, an increase in age (0.0027), household size (0.0032), and education (0.0013), being unregistered (0.0121), working in the industry (0.133) and service (0.0682) sectors elevate the probability of opting for part-time work due to personal or family obligations. In contrast, being married (0.0148), working in career occupations (0.0309), being paid, salaried, or a casual worker (0.0715), and being an employer or self-employed (0.0657) decrease this probability. However, household size, education, and occupation variables for men and registration to SSI for women do not attain statistical significance.

Table 3. Multinomial probit model estimates (average marginal effects)

Reasons	Care responsibilities			Education			Illness or disability			Personal or family obligations			Could not find a full-time job			Nature of the job			
	Marginal effects	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
Gender																			
Female	0.0999*** (0.0035)			0.0004 (0.0031)			-0.0082** (0.0034)			0.023*** (0.0042)			-0.124*** (0.0056)			0.0089 (0.0071)			
Age	-0.0017*** (0.0002)	0.0001 (0.0001)	-0.0036*** (0.0004)	-0.0131*** (0.0005)	-0.017*** (0.0007)	-0.0091*** (0.0006)	0.0014*** (0.0002)	0.0014*** (0.0002)	0.0015*** (0.0002)	0.0027*** (0.0002)	0.0033*** (0.0003)	0.0024*** (0.0003)	0.0012*** (0.0002)	0.0019*** (0.0004)	0.0004 (0.0003)	0.0094*** (0.0004)	0.0104*** (0.0006)	0.0085*** (0.0006)	
Marital status																			
Married	0.0594*** (0.0047)	-0.0021 (0.0027)	0.1222*** (0.0089)	-0.0505*** (0.0059)	-0.0522*** (0.01)	-0.052*** (0.0062)	-0.0094** (0.0044)	-0.0012 (0.0067)	-0.016** (0.0064)	-0.0148** (0.0064)	-0.0159* (0.0092)	-0.0241** (0.0095)	-0.0436*** (0.0082)	-0.0049 (0.0147)	-0.0633*** (0.0087)	0.0589*** (0.0105)	0.0763*** (0.0168)	0.0332** (0.0137)	
Household size	0.0059*** (0.001)	0.0003 (0.0004)	0.012*** (0.002)	-0.0033*** (0.0009)	-0.0034** (0.0016)	-0.0027*** (0.0009)	0.0000 (0.0008)	0.0008 (0.0012)	-0.0008 (0.0012)	0.0032** (0.0013)	0.0016 (0.0016)	0.0048** (0.002)	0.0026 (0.0016)	0.0042 (0.0027)	-0.0013 (0.0019)	-0.0085*** (0.0021)	-0.0035 (0.003)	-0.012*** (0.003)	
Education	0.0002 (0.0005)	0.0001 (0.0002)	0.0002 (0.0009)	0.0021*** (0.0006)	0.0046*** (0.0009)	0.0000 (0.0006)	-0.0038*** (0.0004)	-0.0044*** (0.0006)	-0.0032*** (0.0006)	0.0013** (0.0005)	0.0011 (0.0007)	0.0015* (0.0008)	-0.001 (0.0007)	-0.0047*** (0.0012)	0.0014* (0.0008)	0.0011 (0.001)	0.0034** (0.0014)	0.0000 (0.0014)	
Registration to SSI																			
Unregistered	-0.0014 (0.0053)	-0.0005 (0.0015)	-0.0062 (0.0108)	-0.0552*** (0.0045)	-0.0806*** (0.0064)	-0.0266*** (0.0067)	0.0146*** (0.0031)	0.0179*** (0.0038)	0.0083 (0.0056)	0.0121** (0.0051)	0.0192*** (0.0055)	-0.0075 (0.0097)	0.1005*** (0.0059)	0.1319*** (0.0094)	0.067*** (0.0073)	-0.0706*** (0.0091)	-0.088*** (0.0111)	-0.035** (0.0155)	
Occupation																			
Career	-0.0547*** (0.0042)	-0.0039*** (0.0013)	-0.1062*** (0.0083)	-0.0348*** (0.0063)	-0.0203* (0.0107)	-0.0337*** (0.0068)	-0.0244*** (0.0041)	-0.0192*** (0.0059)	-0.0287*** (0.0053)	-0.0309*** (0.0059)	-0.0123 (0.0085)	-0.0503*** (0.0082)	-0.1155*** (0.007)	-0.1719*** (0.0124)	-0.0655*** (0.0068)	0.2603*** (0.0113)	0.2276*** (0.0176)	0.2845*** (0.0145)	
Sector																			
Industry	0.0664*** (0.0073)	0.0001 (0.0014)	0.133*** (0.0148)	0.026*** (0.0058)	0.0297*** (0.0081)	0.028*** (0.0095)	0.0118*** (0.0045)	0.0106* (0.0064)	0.0137* (0.0075)	0.0652*** (0.0072)	0.0442*** (0.0075)	0.0745*** (0.0127)	0.0875*** (0.0077)	0.1529*** (0.0129)	-0.0052 (0.0088)	-0.2569*** (0.0113)	-0.2375*** (0.0148)	-0.2439*** (0.0187)	
Service	0.0358*** (0.0053)	0.0026 (0.0016)	0.0682*** (0.0104)	0.0273*** (0.0043)	0.0347*** (0.0062)	0.0256*** (0.0065)	0.0149*** (0.004)	0.0174*** (0.0057)	0.0115** (0.0057)	0.059*** (0.0053)	0.0398*** (0.0057)	0.0711*** (0.0098)	0.0685*** (0.0065)	0.0869*** (0.0106)	0.0325*** (0.0085)	-0.2056*** (0.0095)	-0.1814*** (0.0125)	-0.2089*** (0.0154)	
Employment status																			
Paid, salaried, or casual	-0.019*** (0.0061)	-0.0034 (0.0029)	-0.032*** (0.0115)	-0.01** (0.0044)	-0.018*** (0.0063)	-0.0007 (0.0068)	-0.0075 (0.005)	-0.0124 (0.0089)	-0.0059 (0.0058)	-0.0715*** (0.0083)	-0.0691*** (0.0125)	-0.0681*** (0.0116)	0.168*** (0.008)	0.1696*** (0.0143)	0.1244*** (0.0104)	-0.0599*** (0.0114)	-0.0667*** (0.0173)	-0.0176 (0.0169)	
Employer/self-employed	-0.023*** (0.0057)	-0.0039 (0.0029)	-0.0406*** (0.0108)	-0.0198** (0.0078)	-0.0453*** (0.0116)	-0.0035 (0.0096)	-0.0073* (0.0041)	-0.0121 (0.0086)	-0.0056 (0.0052)	-0.0657*** (0.0076)	-0.0682*** (0.0124)	-0.0566*** (0.0109)	0.051*** (0.006)	0.0064 (0.0135)	0.0666*** (0.0074)	0.0649*** (0.0107)	0.123*** (0.0186)	0.0397** (0.0154)	

Statistical significance level: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. Robust standard errors are in parentheses. Reference categories are male, single, registered, earner, agriculture, and unpaid family worker. All regressions control NUTS-1 level regions, and use sample weights. All regressions also contain Age² and account for it when calculating the marginal effects of age. The sample includes part-time workers aged 15–64.

Figure 2. Predicted probabilities by age.

Source: Authors' calculations based on Household Labour Force Survey, with sample weights.

Could Not Find a Full-Time Job: This category represents a distinct reason for part-time work, with notable gender disparities along with the reason for care responsibilities. The magnitude of the gender variable in the total model, including all part-time workers, indicates that men (0.124) are much more likely to work part-time for this reason. Gender disparities can be seen in most demographic and work-related factors. Firstly, an increase in age raises the probability of men working part-time due to could not find a full-time job (on average), while it does not make a significant difference for women. Figure 2 demonstrates that the probability increases until the age of 35 for men and subsequently steadily decreases. Secondly, being married decreases the probability of opting for part-time work due to could not find a full-time job, though this is not statistically significant for men. Thirdly, the effect of education has different directions for men and women. Increasing education levels affect the probability of this category negatively for men (0.0047) and positively for women (0.0014). Finally, the marginal effects of registration to SSI, occupation, and sector variables are considerably more pronounced for men. For example, being unregistered increases the probability by 0.1319 for men but by 0.067 for women. Similarly, working in career occupations decreases the probability by 0.1719 for men but by 0.0655 for women.

Nature of the Job: The nature of the job presents distinct characteristics compared to other reasons for part-time work, particularly in the effects of certain work-related factors. Overall, engaging in earner occupations (0.2603) and working within the industry (0.2569) and service (0.2056) reduces the likelihood of opting for part-time work due to the nature of the job. Conversely, these factors increase the probability of part-time work for all other reasons. Additionally, the magnitudes of the marginal effects associated with these factors surpass those of other categories. An increase in age (0.0094), being married (0.0589), and being an employer or self-employed (0.0649) elevate the probability of part-time work due to the nature of the job. An increase in household size (0.0032), unregistered status (0.0121), and being paid, salaried, or a casual worker (0.0599) decrease this probability. However, household size for men, education, and the paid, salaried, or casual worker variable for women do not achieve statistical significance. Notably, Figure 2 highlights that the probability for this category is notably high for both men and women.

5. Discussion of Results and Conclusion

In this study, we examine the reasons for part-time work in Turkey by concentrating on gender differences. More than 3 million people in Turkey work part-time. In contrast to the global average, where women make up the majority of part-time workers, part-time employment in Turkey is almost equally shared between genders. However, the reasons for part-time work vary by gender. Therefore, using TURKSTAT's 2020 microdata, we analyse the effects of demographic and work-related factors on part-time work reasons for both genders. Unlike other studies that classify reasons for part-time work as voluntary and involuntary, we investigate the reasons separately. The reasons consist of six categories based on part-time workers' responses to the question "Why do you work part-time?" in the Household Labour Force Survey: care responsibilities, education, illness or disability, personal or family obligations, could not find a full-time job, and nature of the job.

Our descriptive results indicate that part-time workers in Turkey are predominantly unregistered, working in earner occupations, and engaged in the agriculture or service sectors. Part-time employment in Turkey demonstrates unique traits while also reflecting

similarities with those in other countries. Notably, the incidence of part-time employment is higher among women, as well as younger and older workers, mirroring trends observed in countries such as the US (Dunn, 2018), Canada (Patterson, 2018), Australia (Cassidy & Parsons, 2017), and numerous European countries (Eurostat, 2023). However, Turkey diverges in terms of the distribution of reasons for part-time work. Unlike in many other countries, where reasons such as care responsibilities or could not find a full-time job are more prevalent, the primary reason for both men and women opting for part-time work in Turkey is the nature of the job. Consequently, the prevalence of other reasons for part-time work is relatively low compared to other countries. Nevertheless, demographic characteristics across categories remain mostly similar. For instance, the mean age is the lowest in the education category, and the proportion of women is higher than men in the care responsibilities category. These findings are consistent with previous studies by Maynard et. al. (2006), Patterson (2018), Cassidy and Parsons (2017), and Dunn (2018). Additionally, the higher rate of men in the could not find a full-time job category aligns with many European countries such as Spain, France, Italy, and Germany, although there are exceptions such as Czechia, Portugal, and Norway (Eurostat, 2023).

The multinomial probit model estimation results reveal gender disparities in the reasons for part-time work, particularly in care responsibilities and the could not find a full-time job. Women are more likely to work part-time due to care responsibilities. Factors such as marital status and household size play a significant role in women's decision to work part-time due to care responsibilities but are insignificant for men. Many studies examining part-time work have highlighted the significance of child-related variables, such as the number of children and having a child under the age of 12, in influencing part-time work decisions (Cam, 2012; Pech et al., 2021; Björk et al., 2020; Blázquez Cuesta & Moral Carcedo, 2014; Kjeldstad & Nymoen, 2012; Barbieri et al., 2019; Tijdens, 2002). However, our study is limited by the absence of child-related variables in the analysis due to their unavailability in the dataset. Nevertheless, the findings underscore the unequal distribution of caregiving responsibilities within families (Lyonette, 2015) and women's endeavours to strike a balance between work and family (Hakim, 2006). In another category marked by gender inequalities, our analysis indicates that men are more inclined to engage in part-time work due to the could not find a full-time job, which contrasts with the findings of Pech et. al. (2021) for the US. Furthermore, factors such as age, registration, occupation, and sector have a bigger impact on men than on women in this category. Examining involuntary part-time work, Görmüş and Erdoğan (2017) for Turkey and Cam (2012) for Britain have suggested that lower education and occupation levels mean higher involuntariness for both genders. Our results show consistency with regard to the impact of occupational factors, and education on men, yet they diverge from this pattern concerning the influence of education level on women. These results reflect the influence of Turkey's traditional male-breadwinner/female-homemaker family structure, as highlighted by İlkkaracan (2012).

Other reasons for part-time work exhibit minimal gender disparities. Although the magnitude of the marginal effects may differ between genders, their direction and statistical significance remain similar. An increase in age positively influences the probability of part-time work reasons such as illness or disability (Gannon & Roberts, 2011), personal or family obligations, and the nature of the job, while it negatively affects education reason. Being registered increases the probability of working part-time due to education and nature

of the job. Furthermore, individuals working in career occupations are more likely to work part-time due to nature of the job and less likely to work part-time for other reasons.

Turkey has the characteristics of a country where female labour force participation is quite low. Expanding part-time work opportunities could serve as an effective strategy to increase women's integration into the workforce (Barbieri et al., 2019; Stavrou et al., 2015; Euwals & Hogerbrugge, 2006). This study aims to understand the motivations of both genders towards part-time employment, focusing on reasons. By examining part-time work from the supply side, we aim to offer insights that can inform policymakers and contribute to a better understanding of labour market dynamics. Future research endeavours could enhance the scope of inquiry by incorporating child-related variables and extending the study over multiple years.

6. References

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